

EXPLORING INTERDISCIPLINARY APPROACHES IN LITERARY STUDIES: BRIDGING LITERATURE WITH PSYCHOLOGY

¹Feruz Boymurodova Ziyot qizi, ²Jonimkulova Sevinch Mavlonjon qizi

¹MA International Education English Teacher, Uzbekistan State World Languages
University

²2nd course student at the UzSWLU, English Philology faculty

Abstract. *Interdisciplinary methods in literary studies mix ideas and methods from different areas to better grasp literary works and their wider meanings. When linking psychology and literature, these combined methods aim to examine the psychological elements within written texts and how these stories show human behavior, feelings, and social concerns. This thesis statement gives informations about interdisciplinary approaches of literary studies and explore them through supplying researches and clear data about the intersection of literature and psychology. In former paragraphs information is outlined about the benefits and reasons why it is important to pay attention to the connection of them, and in latter ones perspectives can be seen which is offered by scholars in order to determining the informations about their intersection.*

Keywords: *Interdisciplinary approach, problem-based learning, Therapeutic effects, empathy, Human Cognition and Development, Cognitive Processes in Literary Interpretation, phantasies, Subjectivity Challenges, Ethical Considerations.*

Аннотация. *В литературоведении междисциплинарные методы сочетают идеи и методы из разных областей, чтобы лучше понять литературные произведения и их более широкий смысл. Объединяя психологию и литературу, эти комбинированные методы сосредоточены на изучении психологических элементов в письменных текстах и на том, как эти истории отражают человеческое поведение, эмоции и социальные проблемы. Это тезисное заявление дает информацию о междисциплинарных подходах к литературоведению и исследует их посредством предоставления исследований и четких данных о пересечении литературы и психологии. В первых абзацах изложена информация о преимуществах и причинах, по которым важно обратить внимание на их связь, а в последних можно увидеть точки зрения, которые предлагаются учеными для определения информации об их пересечении.*

Ключевые слова: *междисциплинарный подход, проблемное обучение, терапевтические эффекты, эмпатия, человеческое познание и развитие, когнитивные процессы в литературной интерпретации, фантазии, проблемы субъективности, этические соображения.*

Annotatsiya. *Adabiyotshunoslikda fanlararo yondashuvlar adabiy asarlarni va ularning ma'nolarini kengroq tushunish maqsadida turli sohalardagi g'oyalari va uslublarni birlashtiradi. Psixologiya va adabiyotni bog'lashda ushbu birlashtirilgan uslublari yozma matnlardagi psixologik elementlarni va ushbu hikoyalar orqali inson xatti-harakati, his-tuyg'ulari va ijtimoiy masalalarni qanday ko'rsatishini ko'rib chiqishga qaratilgan. Ushbu ilmiy tadqiqot ishi adabiyotshunoslikning fanlararo yondashuvlari, shuningdek adabiyot va psixologiya orasidagi bog'liqlik haqida tadqiqotlar va aniq ma'lumotlarni taqdim etish orqali ularni ochib beradi. Avvalgi abzaslarda ularning bir-biriga bog'lanishiga e'tibor berishning afzalliklari va sabablari to'g'risida ma'lumotlar berilgan bo'lsa, keyingilarida esa ularning aloqadorligi haqidagi ma'lumotlarni aniqlash uchun olimlar tomonidan taklif qilinadigan nazariyalarni ko'rish mumkin.*

Kalit so‘zlar: Fanlararo yondashuv, muammolar orqali o‘rganish, Terapevtik effektlar, empatiya, Inson bilishi va rivojlanishi, Adabiy talqindagi kognitiv jarayonlar, fantaziyalar, sub’ektivlik muammolari, axloqiy mulohazalar.

Introduction

Literature Studies is the study of written works of the imagination, of which poetry, drama and narrative fiction constitute today the most familiar types or genres (University of Kentucky, College of Arts and Sciences). Through non-conventional language uses we can explore the complexity and range of human experiences, as a result of that literary works serve as essential resources for examining global events, national histories, individual psychology, social issues such as gender, race, class, religious themes and various art forms. Literature is the store of experiences and individual realities, basically the human psyche, idiosyncrasies, emotions and feelings. Consequently, both literature and psychology are preoccupied with similar issues and both may barrow from each other to offer multiple interpretations and perspectives (Goksen Aras, Atılım University, Kızılcaşar Mah. Incek Ankara 06836, Turkey). It is clear that due to its extensive connections with numerous other areas of study, literary studies emerges as one of the most interdisciplinary fields across academia. This paper reviews overall meaning of connection between Literature and Psychology, additionally, this analysis aims to illuminate precisely the interconnections between literary studies and other disciplines.

Literature review

According to Elizabeth A. Berman and Jodee L. Kuden (in Agriculture to Zoology, 2017): “Interdisciplinary approaches and problem-based learning have permeated all disciplines, with a growing realization that multiple literacies are necessary to fully understand a given subject”. So, initially, according to research by the University of Texas, Permian Basin, psychology and literature intersect in a very dramatic way in first-person stories. These viewpoints provide readers with a deep understanding of the protagonist's thoughts and feelings, although it's crucial to note that they could be unreliable narrators since we only know what they choose to reveal. The use of the first-person narrative can enhance the readers ability to comprehend the characters, even those who may not be likable. As an example, Richard 3 from William Shakespeare’s play, who is marked by physically deformity since birth. While this evokes some sympathy, his real flaw is desire for governing and it calls for murdering his young nephews and others who might be obstacle in his path. Therefore, it is evident that the link between psychology and literature is significant. By portraying psychological concepts through literary means, writers can offer readers deeper insights into psychology, enabling them to form more vivid mental images of psychological phenomena using literary styles. Particularly in poetry, this connection is particularly influential. In general, literature portrays psychology in a more delicate and emotionally impactful manner.

Reasons

Benefits of literature in psychology and psychology in literature are endless and some specific reasons are given here to spread the popularity of connection between them.

Understanding human behavior: The role of connection between psychology and literature is significant in comprehending human behavior more deeply through exploring characters’ motivations, thoughts and emotions which are depicted in literary works.

Enhanced empathy: Empathy is crucial for interpersonal relationships and emotional intelligence, and it is developed through the portrayal of diverse characters and their inner words in literature.

Therapeutic effects: Literature can offer readers a space where it is possible to explore complex emotions, find solace in shared experiences with fictional characters, primarily gain new perspectives which is leading to personal growth.

As an example A. Fox says : Indeed, reading is such a pleasurable and usually private affair that we might be tempted, in our more naïve and less readerly moments, to see it as a ritual divorced from the more active and time-consuming dimensions of our day.

Methods

It is ostensibly true that some scholars are engaged in using qualitative research methods to illustrate how much essence of connection between psychology and literature and this is also accessible to provide some specific semi-structured interviews and focus-group interviews. Although there are some troubles among individuals in this subject and this article mentions some possible methods according to scholars for solving the problems.

Understanding Human Cognition and Development through Narrative: Jerome Bruner, a renowned cognitive psychologist, highlighted the importance of storytelling for understanding human cognition and development. His research emphasized how stories in literature can influence how people see the world and shape their identity.

Exploring Cognitive Processes in Literary Interpretation: Lisa Zunshine's (focuses on cognitive cultural studies) qualitative research has investigated the cognitive processes involved in interpreting narratives, uncovering how literature influences readers' emotions, beliefs, and social interactions.

Enhancing Empathy and Social Understanding through Fiction: Research conducted by Keith Oatley, a cognitive psychologist and fiction writer, includes the information about how literary works can enhance readers' emotional intelligence and foster empathy towards others by immersing them in characters' inner lives and perspectives.

Findings and Discussion

A literary work benefits from psychology in terms of successfully presenting characters, expressing their moods, and bringing the reader into the psychological dimension of human reality. Psychology and study of literature meet in their focus on phantasies, emotions and human soul(Daniel Mengistie Yimer Dire Dawa University, Dire Dawa, Ethiopia). Admittedly, in spite of such benefits, relationship between psychology and literature come with some drawbacks which have been creating people some discomforts.

Subjectivity Challenges: When psychologists exploring the literary forms they conclude the explanations subjectively, so these varying opinions may result in conflicts among conclusions and a lack of consensus.

Limitations in Applications: indications of psychology and literature may not be always appropriate with real-life that the behavior of fictional characters or the storytelling structures may not accurately represent actual human behaviors, restricting the usefulness of these findings for broader psychological theories or practical applications.

Ethical Considerations: Exploring sensitive themes in literature, like trauma or mental health, has the potential to cause distress to participants or readers. Maintaining ethical standards when conducting such research and respecting the integrity of the literary material can present difficulties in these studies.

Conclusion

Literature delves deeply into imaginative works like poetry, narrative fiction, stories and drama in order to influence human's feelings. Nevertheless it is not limited with this, but also can

individual minds and social issues such as gender, race, class, and religious topics. Between them the intersection of literature and psychology unveils a shared interest in understanding human intricacies, presenting diverse interpretations and viewpoints through their interconnectedness.

By implementing benefits for comprehending human behavior, increasing empathy and therapeutic effects the connection of them can be seen clearly, furthermore it can provide solutions for some troubles through scholar's research, like Keith Oatley's that is offered to read literature forms for the purpose of enforcing empathy towards people and enhancing social understanding.

On the other hand some disadvantages can be seen while the connection between them exist, like restrictions in application and the influence of it for ethical subjects.

Generally, the key lies in influence of psychology in literature and literature in psychology.

REFERENCES

1. <https://www.studysmarter.co.uk/explanations/english/key-concepts-in-language-and-linguistics/language-and-technology/>
2. <https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/82271267.pdf>
3. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/earth-and-planetary-sciences/interdisciplinary-approach>
4. [https://www.ieeesem.com/researchpaper/On the Interaction Between Literature and Psychology.pdf](https://www.ieeesem.com/researchpaper/On%20the%20Interaction%20Between%20Literature%20and%20Psychology.pdf)